

Figure S1. Uninterpreted and interpreted seismic section along the N-S segment of F2 showing the low-angle fault geometry and overlying syn-kinematic strata in shallow level of the linkage zone. Note that the growth strata young towards the south and it has been top-truncated at the T70 and T80 horizons.

Upper/brittle crust

 Paleocene-Middle Eocene
 Middle Eocene-Lower Oligocene

Tg = ~65 Ma, T84 = ~46 Ma, T80 = 39 Ma, T70 = ~33 Ma